

////////////////////////////////////
**THE EVOLUTION OF VERNACULAR DESIGN:
CASE STUDIES OF KIMCHI REFRIGERATOR, RICE COOK, AND FLOOR
HEATING SYSTEM**

Da-un ROH / Sungzin CHAE (Corresponding author),
Dept. of Industrial design, Yonsei University / Division of Design and Art, Yonsei University.
szchae@yonsei.ac.kr

ABSTRACT

Vernacular design for the artificial world is the topic of the book *Architecture without Architects*, by Bernard Rudofsky, written in 1964. It attempts to break down our narrow concepts of building art by introducing the unfamiliar world of non-pedigreed architecture. In equal terms, this idea can be adopted to product design area. For want of a generic label, we have called it vernacular, anonymous, spontaneous, indigenous, rural, and local as the case might be. For Koreans it is a remote area for multi-national corporations or global star designers to design appliances and facilities related to life's indispensable staples. Examples include the Kimchi refrigerator, the rice cooker, and floor heating system. Highly educated local designers are developing and commanding the design of local staples and modern vernacular design projects, adapting series of professional conventions of their locality and paying substantial attention to what may be fashionable as well as useful for their neighbor customers. This study explores three cases of modern Korean vernacular design: the Kimchi refrigerator, the rice cooker, and the floor heating system. A new perspective on vernacular design as contemporary high-tech products of necessities is then proposed in a local context.

Keywords: vernacular design, design evolution, Kimchi refrigerator, Rice cooker, Floor heating system

**THREE CASES OF KOREAN VERNACULAR
DESIGN MODERNIZATION**

***FROM THE KIMCHI JAR TO THE KIMCHI
REFRIGERATOR***

Origin of Kimchi: Korean winter pickle

Kimchi (also spelled gimchi, kimchee, or kim chee), is a traditional fermented Korean dish made of vegetables with varied seasonings. Kimchi may also refer to unfermented vegetable dishes. For Koreans, Kimchi refers to a vegetable in salt, from the Chinese word 泡菜. Its principal ingredients are Chinese cabbage, cucumber and radish, and flavorings such as garlic, green onion, ginger and hot pepper. These are mixed and then fermented for a while until the kimchi is ready to serve. This side dish is indispensable on a Korean dining table over the long and cold winters in Korea. It provides many types of vitamins and nutrients and helps with the digestion of the main dish, typically steamed rice. Every year in the late fall, nearly all Korean households prepare a large amount of Kimchi. (Kimjang, or the culture of Kimjang, refers to a family making a large amount of Kimchi as a staple side dish at the beginning of winter.) This is done using fifty to one hundred heads of cabbage and proper equivalent amounts of radish and spices. The resulting product is consumed throughout the winter and into the spring. Documentation survives of a stone Kimchi jar from the Silla dynasty, of approximately 720 AD. This original model resides on the premises of Bup-Ju Temple of Mount Sok-ri. It is 225 cm in depth, with a top lid diameter of 180 cm and an inner space diameter of 85 cm. Two sphere-shaped pieces serve as the top and bottom parts. Four or

five pieces of oval-shaped stone bricks 30-40 cm in length are positioned around each layer of the jar in three layers. It is said that it fed nearly 3,000 Buddhist monks during its use every winter. This type served as the standard for many years. In more modern times starting from the 16th century, Kimchi began to be stored in large earthenware jars about 600mm (w) by 900mm (h), that were buried in the earth of the owner's yard. This typical storage method allowed the fermentation and preservation of the Kimchi naturally. By the 1970s, when most Koreans lived in a house with a garden, this system had become common in Korean households. However, lifestyles were changing dramatically due to urbanization and the popularity of apartment living.

Figure 1. Stone jar in Bup-Ju Temple, 8th Century

Design and laying of Kimchi jar

Kimchi jars, or Kimjang Kimchi Dok, are typically earthenware. Onggi is the Korean pronunciation of pottery or earthenware bowls. The primary material is clay. This type of clayware is glazed and baked at high temperatures in a kiln. The dark-brown glazed model was popular during the Joseon dynasty period of the 14th to the 19th centuries. The process of baking clayware was standardized. A special feature of clayware Kimchi jars helps with the fermentation of Kimchi. Many tiny openings are generated during the clayware baking process. They are only visible with an electron microscope. The typical diameter of these holes is 1/20 of a micrometer, or 0.00022mm, which allows O₂ ventilation but prevents rain from seeping in, as a raindrop is 2000 times larger than the hole. It is an ideal ware offering breathability, waterproofness, and strength, which also performs an optimal function for Kimchi fermentation and storage. Burying it in the ground supports the process

of fermentation and enhances the nutritional quality during long-term storage. The temperature of the earth beneath the surface in wintertime ranges from 0°C to -2°C. An ideal temperature of -0.7°C is required to prevent acidification. To control the level of contact with O₂, the top layer of the Kimchi consisted of a layer of larger outer leaves, which typically were not meant for consumption.

Figure 2. (Left) Section view of a traditional kimchi jar used for storing and fermentation dug into the earth from late fall to early spring

Figure 3. (Right) Kimchi jar dugout with a straw cover

Figure 4. Clayware kimchi jars in the Joseon era, 19th Century

Modern development

From the 1980s, Koreans found little room for the large Kimchi jars and few suitable spots in which to bury them in the dense townhouses and concrete flats that were becoming popular in urban areas. Most households had to purchase small amounts of manufactured Kimchi in plastic pouches at a grocery store, storing it in a corner in a western-style refrigerator for daily meals. This led to two problems; the first was the high cost, which was above what the average household could sustain. The second was that the general taste and quality of the Kimchi produced and stored in this manner were not of the level of the previously homemade variety.

However, some Kimchi brands enjoyed proliferation of their business, despite that most Koreans were grumbling and complaining. Some companies released modified refrigerators with special shelves and sections for Kimchi storage, but then a breakthrough occurred: The kimchi refrigerator as a special unit for fermenting and storing Kimchi was invented and introduced in 1995 by the automotive air-conditioner company Mando. Dimchae was the brand name given to this product by Mando. It was a unit specially designed exclusively for Kimchi. One of its innovative features was an inner wall cooling method that allowed an even distribution of temperature instead of the air circulation system of a conventional refrigerator. It applied a top-loading rather than a front-door style for access, which reduced cool air loss. This design proved to be very efficient for kimchi. It was 50-70L in the size of a small appliance. Dimchae was the answer to the problem of storing and fermenting Kimchi, especially among families that lived in small apartments unit in cities. Major companies such as LG, Daewoo, and Samsung soon facilitated production lines. Many hi-tech designs were developed specifically to meet the storage requirements of various types of kimchi. Options included temperature control and different fermentation processes. Thus was created another large market for an electric appliance, and the kimchi refrigerator became an important export item to China and Japan, where Kimchi was becoming popular. In a consumer survey aimed at Korean housewives conducted by a well-established Korean media agency in 2004, the Kimchi refrigerator was ranked first as the most-wanted household appliance. Kimchi refrigerators have carved out a significant niche as a new appliance.

Figure 5. (Left) Hanil Stainless Co., Bio-cubic Kimchi storage container

Figure 6. (Right) Kimchi making in modern age

Figure 7. (Left) Mando Co., Dimchae, 1995 and (Right) New Dimchae, 2010

Period	Changes of kimchi jars
Three Kingdoms (4~8 C.)	A stone jar
Goryeo Dynasty (918 ~ 1392)	Pottery with a dark-brown glaze, known as Onggi
Joseon Dynasty~before the restoration of independence (1392~1945)	
1950s~1970s	
1980s	A plastic or stainless steel container
After the 1990s	The Kimchi refrigerator

Table 1. Changes of Kimchi Jars over Time

FROM A PIG IRON JAR TO A HIGH-TECH PRESSURE POT

Old iron jars

Currently rice cookers hold the rice that is eaten at every meal in Korea. They work by boiling or steaming, with the rice, absorbing water as it cooks. In contrast to South Asian long-grain rice, Koreans eat japonica-style rice, which is a short-grained variety characterized by its unique stickiness and texture. To cook the grain into a tasty meal, a high-pressure jar consisting of thick pig iron used to be common. This was a pig iron or stone jar known as a Sott or Cheong of the type excavated at the ruins of an old civilization around the 1st century¹. Gama Sott is the term given to a typical traditional large iron jar fixed on a fire place. Gama refers to a heating chamber, similar to the western concept of an oven. Ancient Koreans put an earthenware jar with holes on the bottom on a water containing pot. When the water was boiled, the steam from the pot

¹ Rice farming is believed to have started in Korea, around 3000 B.C. In the 1977 excavation of Heunamri, Yeosu, in Gyeonggi, carbonized rice (炭火米) was found, and another discovery was made Pyongyang, South Pyongan, dating to the Bronze Age. These findings show that rice farming and cooking were a part of the Bronze Age civilization in Korea.

comes through and cooks the rice in the earthenware on top. The dimensions of the iron jar increased over time, and this large jar tended to be fixed permanently on the fireplace for general purposes. The development of iron metallurgy allowed cooking in the iron container directly. Another innovation was to introduce specially designed hemispherical heavy iron jar cover with a knob handle in the center. This lid holds the high-pressure steam, which saves fuel and enhances the taste and nutrition of the cooked rice. When the lid is laid upside down, the concave face can be used as a warmer, and the knob handle in the center could be used in wine distilling.

Figure 8. (Left) Sott (pig iron) jar and earthenware cookers (top of the jar), fireplace, (Right) A.D. 357, Korea, Sott and earthenware top, and a fireplace are seen in a mural

Figure 9. Traditional kitchen top with Gama Sott

Figure 10. (Left) stone jar (Dol Sott), Joseon dynasty, 100mm h * 205mm in diameter, (Right) Soap stone jar, Joseon dynasty, 210mm h * 320mm in diameter

Modern jars

However, the traditional Korean cast iron cauldron was far from convenient. It had some defects. First, the iron was heavy to the point that it was not easy to wash, and the lid was not easy to pick up or put down. It also had poor energy performance, as it took a great deal of wood to heat up and boil what

was inside. In contrast, a rice cooker made of aluminum appeared. It required less heat than a cast iron pot or cauldron, to cook. The Brown Rice Cooker made by Lucky Aluminum in 1975 reflected the new social trend. It was made in a similar shape to the traditional iron cooker, with pressure cooker technology. The final result was a well-designed brown rice cooker in which tradition was harmonized with the latest technology. This aluminum or stainless steel rice pot was heated on a portable cooking stove or a small kitchen range.

Figure 11. Lucky Aluminum Co. rice jar

Electro-mechanized version

The modern version of the jar is the electric rice cooker, popular in Korea as it simplifies the process of cooking by applying electronics that allow one to set a timer so that the rice will be ready for the morning meal. In December of 1956, the Toshiba Corporation brought the first commercially successful automated electric rice cooker to the market. It used a double-chamber indirect rice cooking method. Rice was placed into the rice pot, and water into a surrounding container. When the water in the outer pot boiled off, the temperature of the pot rose rapidly. A bimetallic thermostat then activated and automatically turned off the cooker to prevent burning of the cooked rice. Soon, Toshiba was producing 200,000 rice cookers per month for the Japanese market. Four years later, rice cookers could be found in half of Japanese homes. The rice cooker can also keep rice moist and warm. Rice kept warm in this manner remains edible for several hours, so that rice need be made only once per day. These inventions utilized microprocessor-controlled cooking cycles, pressure cooking, and induction heating, which generated heat directly within the inner cooking bowl itself while varying the pressure via a control mechanism termed a "dual-pressure" method that created repeated pressure/release cycles during the cooking cycle. These products required various materials (e.g., copper, pure carbon,

ceramic, diamond power coating) for the inner cooking bowl due to their high heat conductivity and utilized multiple induction heating elements. They also employed a mechanism to collect and return the boiled over liquid to the inner rice bowl. The double-chamber indirect cooking model took more time to complete the cooking and consumed more electricity. This model was gradually phased out starting in the 1960s. Today, electric rice cookers utilize an insulated outer container and an inner removable bowl that is often coated with a non-stick surface, e.g., of Teflon², and typically stamped with water-level graduations marked in cups of rice used. The rice cup measure is normally based on the traditional Korean-Japanese measurement system.

It takes about 30 minutes (or a bit less than 1 hour, including the post-cooking water-absorption time) for most of electric rice cookers to complete their cooking cycles. Rice may be soaked prior to cooking, which saves fuel, decreases the cooking time, and minimizes exposure to high temperatures, and thus decreasing the stickiness of the rice. For some varieties, soaking improves the texture of the cooked rice by increasing the expansion of the grains. Some advanced models which utilize built-in micro-processors can back calculate the cooking start time from an arbitrary given finish time. The time required for cooking the rice depends on the amount of rice, the ability of heating elements (wattage of the heating element, voltage of the power source, or the heat generation ability of the element), the room temperature and the atmospheric pressure, thus showing great variance. There are pressure-cooker models at the higher end of the electric rice cooker range which are not influenced by atmospheric pressure. These special abilities of the high-end models are intentional to distinguish them from the lower-end simple models that are economical but have only simple functions. The pressure-cooking models can raise the water's boiling point higher, e.g., from 100°C at 1.0atm up to about 110°C at 1.4atm, and are generally believed to produce a better result. Deploying a thick and heavy inner jar and lid is a special feature of most Korean pressure models. It can hold higher pressure and provide an even distribution of the warming

² This is a very popular inner rice bowl made of agalmatolite and cast iron.

temperature after the cooking cycle. This design is a modern interpretation of the combination of the traditional heavy iron jar and cover of Gama Sott.

Figure 12. Electric rice cookers, Apollo electric rice cooker (end of 1970s), Cuckoo pressure rice cooker of Sungkwang Electronics Co. (1998) and a Cuckoo pressure rice cooker (2010)

Period	Changes in rice cookers
Three Kingdoms (4~8 C.)	A pig iron jar A stone jar
Goryeo Dynasty (918~1392)	
Joseon Dynasty~before the restoration of independence (1392~1945)	A pig iron jar, known as Gama Sott A soap stone jar A stone jar
1950s-1970s	An aluminum pot A pressure rice cooker: Brown rice cooker
1980s	An electric rice cooker
After the 1990s	An electric pressure rice cooker

Table 2. Changes of rice cookers over time

Figure 13. The evolution of Korean rice cookers: cast iron pot/cooker, rice cooker, electric pressure rice cooker

FROM ONDOL, THE KOREAN FLOOR HEATING SYSTEM TO THE HEATED STONE BED

Ondol: origin

Ondol, also called Gudeul, refers to heating stones or stones heated by fire. It is a traditional floor heating system in Korea. The traditional type of Ondol³ originated in the Goguryeo Dynasty, B.C.37~A.D.668.

³ Many Ondol are found in the ruins of the Three Kingdoms period, 4 C.~8 C., Baekje Dynasty, B.C.18~A.D.660, and Silla Dynasty, B.C. 57~A.D. 935. There are mural paintings of Ondol in Anak Tomb No.3 of Goguryeo.

According to the old Chinese document *Gudangseo* (舊唐書), Koreans in mountainous areas constructed a long hole, akin to a tunnel, underneath the house that contained fire and smoke that warmed the interior space during the winter. This is a clear description of Ondol. We find the basic design of ancient Ondol has survived to the modern age with few changes.

Figure 14. L-shape Ondol of Goguryeo Dynasty, B.C.37-A.D.668, old settlement, Daepyung, Bookchang (N. Korea)

However, Ondol was initially invented as a heat source for cold areas and mainly for people of the lower classes. It spread increasingly to the upper classes after the middle of the Goryeo period. Ondol became popular and spread to not only the common people but also the royal family during the Joseon Dynasty period (1392-1910). By the 1950s, typical Ondol design was to flow heat and smoke beneath the floor of living and sleeping rooms. Before modernization, there were a couple of fireplaces or fire holes between the sleeping room and the kitchen. Korean geography places it in the Siberian high continental climate zone. It is very cold in winter and very hot in summer. People use firewood and dried straw to cook and to warm the floor. Hot smoke travels under the floor through smoke passages to a chimney. From the 1950s, the Korean government pushed a nationwide program of fire place renovation to prevent deforestation. The new designs suggested had several innovative features. First, they used a new fuel source of a standard soft coal briquette for burning. Secondly, they involved boiling water in plastic or steel pipes wrapping around fireproof materials that passing beneath the floor. The third important feature is the separation of the fire compartment and the kitchen by replacing smoke with a hot water pipe as the floor heating element. This eliminated smoke and the carbon monoxide poisoning danger by furnishing a fire place with good ventilation.

Figure 15. Typical home life in the 10th century in Korea

Construction and operation

The fireplace (also known as a firebox or a fire hole) was used (A) where firewood or another source burns and emits heat at the front end. The smoke passage (B) lies under the floor stones/stone slabs covered by red-yellow flooring clay (C). At each end of the smoke passages, a groove/trap collects smoke/dust just before the chimney (Ds). The conventional type of Ondol adapts a ground dug groove and uses bricks or foundation stones to support the groove wall. A series of flat floor stones are laid over the bricks and stones, and pieces of small stones are located between the flat floor stones' crevices to prevent smoke or fire from escaping. Wet clay is applied evenly on the top of the flat floor stones and crack filling pieces as the interior room flooring. Glossy oiled paper was used as a finishing touch for the floor, as this suited the lifestyle of Koreans, who like to sit on the warm floor. According to the smoke-passage route layout, Ondol designs can be classified into the single passage model (Types 1 and 2), the multiple passage model (Types 4, 5, and 6), or the multi-passage model with several pillars in the form of a poly column style (Type 3). The ceiling of the smoke passage near the fireplace is higher than the chimney. The height is gradually reduced to the chimney (E) so as to spread heated smoke evenly and to enhance its flow.

Figure 16. Construction of Ondol

Figure 17. Types of Ondol

Modern Ondol: Smokeless coal briquette furnace, electric mats, and stone beds

The conventional type of fireplace/fire hole was popular by 1950s. However, with the crisis of deforestation and development of the coal mining, a new type of home furnace was introduced in urban areas as the initial stage of change. This change resulted in several improvements. Smokeless coal briquettes have a very high concentration of energy. They are small but emit a large volume of heat. Upon catching fire, they burn for continuously up to eight hours. As a result, housewives did not need to refuel the fireplace or wake up to feed firewood in to it in the middle of the night in winter. Thus, they were economic and efficient. In 1952, the Korean government introduced the standard type of coal briquette. They were cylindrical briquettes with 9, 19, 20, 21, or 22 holes. While this type became a regular feature of home heating and cooking, there was a lethal side-effect. Smokeless coal briquettes emitted a substantial amount of carbon monoxide gas (briquette gas), and in under certain conditions, they caused poisoning sickness and even death. Sulfur dioxide also contributed to air pollution, structural corrosion, and acid rainfall.

Figure 18. 19-22-hole cylindrical briquette, and an image of a woman carrying a cylindrical briquette to replace a burnt one

Thus, the Korean government and researchers started an intensive furnace improvement search for a new type of Ondol. One of the results was the panel heating method, which used hot water pipes. Ironically, an American architect (Frank Lloyd Wright⁴) was the originator of this idea. It involved the somewhat simple method of replacing the smoke passages with a hot water pipeline under the floor. It used a briquette-fired boiler.

In the 1960s, an improved model known as the Sae Ma Eul Boiler-heater (New Village Boiler) was introduced. Its important advantage was the simple construction. It did not require lifting of the entire floor. A bundle of PVC piping for hot water circulation is laid on an existing floor of the room. Then, cement work covers it. As this was less expensive and could be completed quickly, it was very popular with low income families who lived in inexpensive housing. The necessity of finishing the pipeline and boilers room by room is the major drawback of this system. When central heating system was introduced in 1970s, this problem was relieved, after which the oil-fired boiler expanded the market for hot water floor heating construction in apartments. LNG networks in metropolitan areas in the 1980s provided another breakthrough for cleaner floor heating systems.

Figure 19. The traditional Korean floor heating system

Figure 20. A modern living room and hot water pipeline flooring under construction

At present, Korean lifestyles involving sit-down work, rest, and meal incorporates the sedentary lifestyle of

⁴ He said that the feeling of Korean Ondol was like a warm spring, allowing him to feel too comfortable while not feeling heat or hot air anywhere.

Western culture. It is a mixed cultural mode. According to Valerie Gelezeau, a French sociologist who wrote her doctoral dissertation on apartments of Korea, "Korean apartments may look westernized—with western-style structures and flush toilets—but this is true only in terms of the construction materials and equipment. For example, they use a heating system that is based on the traditional method, in which the floor is heated up. Korean-style living is based on this heating system, and it is uniquely. The current heating system in Korea is in fact the technological perfection of the traditional Ondol system." She also wrote about the lifestyle of Korean apartment residents, which, according to her, is largely a mix of western and Korean patterns. Korean living patterns and the use of furniture resemble those of western countries, but they created something that is unique to Koreans. Using an electrical mat refers to the nomadic life of floor sitting. In keeping with this, the heated stone bed presents a Korean-Westernization hybrid. The heated stone bed is a good example of Korea's unique housing culture, which combines the traditional Ondol heating system and the western bedroom system. Since its debut in the early 90s, the stone bed has created a sensational response in the market. By the late 1990s, the popular product recorded hundreds of thousands of Korean won in sales per hour through distribution channels including TV home shopping.

Figure 21. Stone bed with an electric heater inside, Jangsoo (Long Life) Co.

Figure 22. Electric mat, Dayeon Tech. Co.

Period	Changes of Ondol
Three-Kingdoms (4~8 C.)	A partial heating stone
Goryeo Dynasty (918~1392)	Heating floor stones, Ondol
Joseon Dynasty~before the restoration of independence (1392~1945)	
1950s~1970s	Briquette-fired floor stones A briquette-fired boiler Sae Ma Eul Boiler
1980s	A oil-fired boiler
After the 1990s	A gas-fired boiler
	A heating stone bed
	An electric mat

Table 3. Changes of Ondol over time

Figure 23. The evolution of Ondol

Figure 24. An electronic mat and heated stone bed as a type of heterogenic floor heating

CONCLUSION

With the influx of western culture, Korean everyday lifestyles became more westernized, but not the diet. Cooked rice and the rice cooker, the Kimchi refrigerator, and the Ondol heating system (floor heating) still appear in Koreans home, specialized for a hi-tech and domestic experience. These cases clearly show the proliferation of modern vernacular design. It is the charming progress of the Gama Sott (the cast iron pot) to the inner steel bowl of the rice cooker controlled by built-in microprocessors, and of a fireplace with a firewood Ondol system to a hot water pipeline with LNG energy or an electric heater. Contemporary vernacular design becomes the major design after adjustment of the concepts of amateurism and traditionalism. The majority of people who spend their lives on their own land use local designs such as chopsticks and rice bowls, or fork, knives and dishes. The products of

multinational corporations or the works of renowned star designers have little to do with the principle requirements of people, such as eating, socializing, resting, and sleeping. There are splendid vernacular designs for the fundamental needs of people of the real world. Each society has wide range of contemporary versions of vernacular designs found nowhere else. The survival of contemporary vernaculars tells of their design excellence per se. They were developed through close research of the local situation, intensive performance testing, and a sophisticated level of detail, while at the same time they are equipped with hi-tech computer chips and special metallurgical products. The function of contemporary vernacular design requires a domestic, aesthetic, and indigenous factor as well as quality considerations of local customs.

Findings and implications

- Vernacular design, an artifact of endemic everyday lifestyle, that has evolved long time period acquires strong inertia, and resists low priced imported substitution.
- Local designers who have grown in local culture command superb ability to design vernacular artifacts integrating available hi-techs. No designer or engineer of outside dares those potentials of them.
- Companies producing vernacular designs that answer local requirements rule local and national market with stable status.
- Narration and perspective of vernacular design history could be excellent alternative for Western civilization centered conventional historical rhetoric, such as "from Arts and Crafts to Bauhaus" or "Industrial Revolution to Information Big Bang."

	Name	Introduction Time	Building materials	Energy for working	Devices and Mechanism	Description
Kimchi jar and refrigerator	Onggi	14th century	Clay, dark-brown glaze	non	Natural geothermal-energy	It is still widely use for storing and fermenting various food stuff and Kimchi as well.
	Kimchi refrigerator	1995	Plastic, steel, etc.	Electricity	Inner wall cooling system, Top-loading door type	Its performance for storing food is said better than typical front loading one.
Rice cooker	Pig iron jar, Gama sott	16th century	Cast Iron	Wood fire	Heavy iron cap contains high pressure of hot steam and even heat conduction.	Some traditional restaurant still uses for general boiling and cooking purpose.
	Aluminum pot	1975	Aluminum drawing	Coal or petrol fire	Fast heat conductivity	The shape is similar to cast iron pot. It is light weight, but provides moderate taste.
	Pressure rice cooker	1990s	Plastic, steel, etc.	Electricity	High pressure that controlled by built-in micro processors	Many model shapes round corner and general cubic form.
Ondol Floor heating system	Ondol	9th-10th century	Stone, clay	Wood fire	Warm air(smoke) passes under floorstone	However its original construction is almost no longer found, its name is still using.
	Boiler with hot waterline	1950s	Plastic, metal, concrete-cement, etc.	Briquette, oil, gas, LNG	Warm water or air passes in pipe underneath floor	Conventional LNG or oil fuel boilers are heat resource for water pipeline.
	Stone bed	1990s	Stone, wood, etc.	Electricity	Electric charged hot wire runs through in bedstone	It is a sort of heater-bed mattress combination.

Table 4. The evolution of vernacular design

REFERENCES

Valérie Gelézeau (2007) Apartment Republic. Seoul: Humanitas book, 189P

Bernard Rudofsky (1987) Architecture Without Architects. University of New Mexico Press

H.J.Lee (2000) A study on Kimchi, Korean Traditional Dishes, Culture. Journal of Korean Contents Study, Vol.18, 85-99

T.C. Chong, Y.H. Yun (2005) Cast iron pot. Asian comparative folklore, Vol.28, 13-56

Hyunjoo Kang et al. (2009) Design that resembles us Korean design heritage 2008. Korea Design Foundation publisher

Sukho Kim (2007) Porous and Pottery with Dark Brown Glaze. Journal of Korean Contents Study, Vol. 7, No. 10, 157-164

Dukyung Choi (2008) Spread and Structure of Ondol and Influence in Korean's life culture. Korean Agricultural History Studies, Vol. 7, No.2, 33-67

B.I. Park, H.T. Seok, K.G. Kim (1995) The Historical Changes of Ondol. Korean Journal of Air-Conditioning and Refrigeration Engineering. Vol. 24, No. 6, 613-627